

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4

2026

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI TO'LOV INFRATUZILMASINI SHAKILLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI: TARIXIY, ILMIY HAMDA BOZOR TAHLILI	32
A.A. Akbarov, X.R. Aliyev	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI VA ULARNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI.....	42
Karayev Payzillaxon Yusufxonovich	
TURIZM KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARINING ROLI.....	47
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA EKOLOGIK SOLIQLAR VA TO'LOVLAR TIZIMI TAHLILI	53
Sadullayev Rasulbek Palvanbayevich, Abdolnizozov Murodbek Madiyarovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA IJTIMOYIY HIMOYA TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA AMALGA OSHIRILAYOTGAN ISHLAR VA TIZIMGA KIRITILAYOTGAN O'ZGARISHLAR.....	59
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna, Aripova Kamola Botir qizi	
MINTAQAVIY RIVOJLANISHNI KOMPLEKS BAHOLASH VA PROGNOZLASHDA EKONOMETRIK VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT USULLARINING INTEGRATSIYASI	64
Namazov Gafur Shokulovich	
BALIQCILIK SUBYEKTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DUNYO MAMLAKATLARINING O'RNI	69
Beglayev Uchqun Xurramovich	
KAMBAG'ALLIK FENOMENINING IJTIMOYIY-IQTISODIY VA NAZARIY-KONTSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	75
Musulmonova Shahlo Nasriddinovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HISOB VA BIZNES JARAYONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	81
Artikova R.A.	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA DIVIDEND TO'LASH QOBILİYATI KOEFFITSIYENTINING MAQBUL ORALIG'INI ANIQLASH VA UNING INVESTITSION SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	88
Ibragimov G'anjion G'ayratovich	
STRATEGIES TO RAISE AWARENESS OF NATURAL POLLUTION AMIDST RISING POPULATION DENSITY AND GDP PER CAPITA IN UZBEKISTAN	93
Axliddin Aropitdinovich Valiyev, Askarov Farhod Rakhmatovich	
РОЛЬ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ESG-ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОМ РАЗВИТИИ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ.....	99
Айматова Фарида Хуразовна	
KORXONALARDA INVESTITSION FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANISHINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	107
Shukurillaev Jahongir Botir o'g'li	
DEHQON XO'JALIKLARINI MOLIYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDA KREDITLAR MIQDORINI DIFFERENSIYALLASHTIRISH: NAZARIY VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR	113
Xakimov Zafar Ibragimovich	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	118
Tadjimirzayev Anvar Abduvoxidovich, Batirova Raxima Abdujabborovna	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA HUDUDIY MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	124
Muhammadieva Nodira	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT DAVRIDA HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISHNI STATISTIK HISOBLASH METODOLOGIYASINI QAYTA BAHOLASH MEZONLARI (SCOPUS VA WEB OF SCIENCE DA INDEKSLANGAN ILMIY NASHRLAR TAHLILI ASOSIDA).....	131
Santjar Abdumurodovich Sattorov	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING HUDUDIY-IQTISODIY OMILLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	139
Allamuratova Perida Maxsetbaevna	

XORAZM VILOYATIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING ROLI VA AHAMIYATI	144
Ro'zmatova Farahongiz Bekmurotovna, Yarmetova Nargiza Shiximbayevna	
AHOLINI IJTIMOIIY TA'MINOT TIZIMINING TAMOIYILLARI VA UNING MOLIYAVIIY MEXANIZMLARI	148
Xusanov Baxodir Sheraliyevich	
MAHALLIIY VA XALQARO TURIZM BOZORIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISH OMILLARI, TAMOIYILLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI	152
Alikulov Samar Abdurashidovich	

MAHALLIY VA XALQARO TURIZM BOZORIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISH OMILLARI, TAMOYILLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI

Alikulov Samar Abdurashidovich

Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti Samarqand filiali, professor v.b.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada mahalliy va xalqaro turizm bozorida raqobatbardoshlikni shakllantirish omillari, tamoyillari va mexanizmlari kabi muhim masalalar yoritilgan. Turizm raqobatbardoshlikning nazariy asoslari va uning amaliy jihatlari o'rganilgan. Xususan, yo'nalishlarning jozibadorligi, infratuzilma darajasi va uning iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta'siri hisobga olingan holda, mazkur tushunchaning ko'p qirrali ekanligi ko'rsatilgan.

Shuningdek, ilmiy adabiyotlar tahlili asosida ushbu masalaning dolzarbligi keng yoritilgan. Adabiyotlar sharhi keng qamrovda shakllantirilgan bo'lib, unda metodologik masalalar, olingan natijalar hamda muhokama qilinadigan jihatlar qamrab olingan.

Maqolaning yakuniy qismida xulosa va foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati keltirilgan. Maqola ko'plab manbalar va yangi ma'lumotlar bilan boyitilgan, turli qarashlar, g'oyalar va nazariyalar tahlil qilinib, ulardan samarali foydalanilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Jahon iqtisodiy forumi, indeks, mezonlar, destinatsiyalar, indikatorlar, omillar, metodologiya, barqarorlik, PROMETHEE usuli, klasterlar, industriyalar, infratuzilma, monitoring, strategiya, marketing, faol raqobatbardoshlik, global va ekologik omillar, kompleks qarorlar, moslashuvchanlik.

Abstract. The article examines important issues related to the formation of competitiveness in both local and international tourism markets, including the factors, principles, and mechanisms that shape it. The theoretical foundations of competitiveness in tourism, as well as its practical aspects, are analyzed. In particular, taking into account the attractiveness of destinations, the level of infrastructure development, and their impact on economic growth, it is demonstrated that the concept of competitiveness is multifaceted.

Furthermore, based on an analysis of scientific literature, the relevance of this issue is comprehensively highlighted. The literature review is presented extensively and covers methodological aspects, obtained results, as well as various issues discussed within the study.

In the final part of the article, conclusions and a list of references are provided. The article is enriched with numerous sources and new data, and various perspectives, ideas, and theoretical approaches are analyzed and effectively utilized.

Key words: World Economic Forum, index, criteria, destinations, indicators, factors, methodology, sustainability, PROMETHEE method, clusters, industries, infrastructure, monitoring, strategy, marketing, active competitiveness, globalization and ecology, integrated solutions, adaptability.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются важные вопросы, связанные с формированием конкурентоспособности на местном и международном туристическом рынке, включая факторы, принципы и механизмы её обеспечения. Исследованы теоретические основы конкурентоспособности в туризме, а также её практические аспекты. В частности, с учётом привлекательности туристических направлений, уровня развития инфраструктуры и их влияния на экономическое развитие показано, что понятие конкурентоспособности является многогранным.

Кроме того, на основе анализа научной литературы подробно раскрыта актуальность рассматриваемой проблемы. Обзор литературы представлен достаточно широко и охватывает методологические вопросы, полученные результаты, а также обсуждение значимых аспектов, связанных с данной тематикой.

В заключительной части статьи представлены выводы и список использованной литературы. Статья обогащена многочисленными источниками и новыми данными, проведён анализ различных подходов, идей и теорий, а также показана эффективность их применения.

Ключевые слова: Всемирный экономический форум, индекс, критерии, туристические дестинации, индикаторы, факторы, методология, устойчивость, метод PROMETHEE, кластеры, индустрии, инфраструктура, мониторинг, стратегия, маркетинг, активная конкурентоспособность, глобализация и экология, комплексные решения, адаптивность.

KIRISH

Ushbu bozorlardagi raqobatbardoshlikni belgilovchi omillar, tamoyillar va mexanizmlarni chuqur o'rganish turizm sektorining barqaror rivojlanishi uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega (Sobirov et al., 2023). Jahon bozorida samarali ishtirok etish va xorijiy sayyohlarni jalb qilish maqsadida turizm sohasida raqobatbardosh takliflar yaratish, shuningdek, rivojlanish darajasi past bo'lgan mamlakatlar uchun ilg'or xorijiy modellarni moslashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu esa ularning xalqaro bozorda o'z mavqeini mustahkamlashiga xizmat qiladi (Деяк & Kushnir, 2022).

Turizm raqobatbardoshlikning nazariy va amaliy jihatdan o'rganilishi, xususan, yo'nalishlarning jozibadorligi, samaradorligi hamda iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta'siri hisobga olingan holda, ushbu tushunchaning ko'p qirrali ekanligini ko'rsatadi (Okroshidze et al., 2024). So'nggi o'ttiz yil ichida turizm yo'nalishlarining raqobatbardoshligiga qaratilgan tadqiqotlarga qiziqish sezilarli darajada oshgan bo'lib, buning natijasida nufuzli ilmiy jurnallarda 1100 dan ortiq maqola nashr etilgan (Khelashvili & Okroshidze, 2025).

Mazkur holat global turizmning kengayishi va raqobat muhitining murakkablashuvi bilan izohlanadi. Natijada xalqaro tashkilotlar va tadqiqot institutlari tomonidan turizm raqobatbardoshligini baholash uchun standartlashtirilgan doiralar, indikatorlar hamda hisobot metodologiyalari ishlab chiqilgan (Khelashvili & Okroshidze, 2025). Bunday yondashuvlar turizm bozorida faoliyat yurituvchi subyektlarga o'z raqobatbardoshligini baholash va uni takomillashtirish imkonini beradi (Hefny, 2023; Kim et al., 2021).

Xususan, Jahon Iqtisodiy Forumi tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan Sayohat va turizm raqobatbardoshlik indeksi mamlakatlarning ushbu sektorni barqaror va moslashuvchan rivojlantirish qobiliyatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va siyosatlarni baholashda global mezon sifatida xizmat qiladi (Hefny, 2023). Ushbu indeks turizm yo'nalishlarining raqobatbardoshligini aniqlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi hamda mamlakatlarga o'z pozitsiyalarini yaxshilashda ko'maklashadi (Khelashvili & Okroshidze, 2025; Novais et al., 2015).

Biroq, mazkur indeks har doim ham mamlakatlarning solishtirma ustunligi bilan bir qatorda yuqori raqobatbardoshlikni anglatavermaydi. Chunki ushbu omillarning o'zaro nisbatlari mamlakatlarning rivojlanish darajasiga bog'liq bo'ladi (González-Rodríguez et al., 2023). Shu sababli turizm sanoatida raqobatbardoshlikni shakllantirishda faqat iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarga emas, balki tabiiy resurslar, texnologik taraqqiyot hamda boshqaruv samaradorligi kabi omillarga ham alohida e'tibor qaratish zarur (Hong, 2009).

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Turizm sohasidagi raqobatbardoshlikni baholash bo'yicha ko'plab nazariy modellar va amaliy tadqiqotlar mavjud bo'lib, ular orasida biznes, destinatsiyalar va milliy miqyosdagi raqobatbardoshlikni aniqlashga qaratilgan yondashuvlar alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi (Okroshidze et al., 2024).

Ayniqsa, Jahon Iqtisodiy Forumining ko'p mezonli yondashuvi asosida har ikki yilda bir marta e'lon qilinadigan Sayohat va turizm raqobatbardoshligi indeksi jamoatchilik e'tiborini keng jalb etgan (Vošta & Abrahám, 2015). Mazkur indeks destinatsiyalarning makro darajadagi qiyosiy tahlilini ta'minlab, ularning raqobatbardoshligini baholash imkonini beradi (Ataberk, 2022).

Ushbu indeksning muhim afzalligi shundaki, u 140 dan ortiq mamlakatni keng qamrovli indikatorlar asosida muntazam ravishda baholaydi hamda ularni o'zaro taqqoslash imkonini yaratadi (Vošta & Abrahám, 2015). Jahon Iqtisodiy Forumi 1979-yildan buyon mamlakatlarning raqobatbardoshligini baholab kelmoqda va turizm sohasidagi raqobatbardoshlikni mamlakat samaradorligini belgilovchi institutlar, siyosatlar va omillar majmui sifatida talqin etadi (Okroshidze et al., 2024).

Mazkur tizim mamlakatlarning turizm sanoatini rivojlantirish uchun qanchalik qulay sharoitlar yaratganini aks ettiradi hamda ularga o'z strategiyalarini optimallashtirishda yordam beradi (Okroshidze et al., 2024; Ubavic, 2016). Ushbu indeksni hisoblashda turizm sanoatining rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi 14 ta asosiy omil, jumladan,

tabiiy, madaniy-tarixiy va inson resurslari holati, narxlar raqobatbardoshligi, xalqaro ochiqlik va xavfsizlik kabi mezonlar inobatga olinadi (Shabanova et al., 2022; Sobirov et al., 2023).

Mazkur ko'rsatkichlar asosida mamlakatlar turizm sohasidagi global reytinglarda o'rin egallaydi. Bu esa ularning investitsiyaviy jozibadorligini hamda xalqaro turizm oqimlarini jalb qilish salohiyatini belgilaydi (Marynyak & Stetsko, 2021; Safarov & Janzakov, 2021).

Shu bilan birga, har bir mamlakatning o'ziga xos turizm salohiyati va uning asosiy elementlari — tabiiy landshaftlar, dengizlar, daryolar, tog'lar, mineral suvlar, shifobaxsh buloqlar va iqlim sharoitlari, shuningdek, boy madaniy-tarixiy meros — turizm raqobatbardoshligini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu tabiiy va madaniy boyliklarning saqlanishi hamda ulardan barqaror foydalanish raqobatbardoshlikni ta'minlashda majburiyatdan ko'ra zaruriyat sifatida namoyon bo'ladi (Uca & Yüncü, 2020).

Jahon Iqtisodiy Forumining turizm raqobatbardoshligi hisobotiga ko'ra, mamlakatlar besh asosiy mezon — muhitning qulayligi, turizm siyosati, infratuzilma, milliy resurslar va madaniy resurslar bo'yicha baholanadi. Mazkur baholash tizimi mamlakatlarning turizm sohasidagi ustunliklarini aniqlash va mavjud kamchiliklarini bartaraf etishga xizmat qiladi (Göral & Tengilimoğlu, 2018).

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Ushbu baholash tizimi mamlakatlarning turizm sohasidagi o'ziga xos ustunliklarini aniqlash hamda ularning zaif tomonlarini takomillashtirishga xizmat qiladi. Bundan tashqari, mazkur modellar turizm yo'nalishlari menejerlari uchun ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etib, ularga raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish bo'yicha samarali qarorlar qabul qilishda yordam beradi (Díaz-Padilla et al., 2023).

Biroq, Sayohat va turizm raqobatbardoshlik indeksi o'zining hisoblash metodologiyasi bo'yicha muayyan tanqidlarga uchragan bo'lib, shu sababli u har doim ham destinatsiyaning raqobatbardoshligini aniq o'lchovchi universal vosita sifatida e'tirof etilmaydi (Liu et al., 2021). Shu bois turizm raqobatbardoshligini baholashda muqobil modellar va metodologiyalarni ishlab chiqishga ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda, ayniqsa, madaniy o'ziga xoslik, ekologiya va atrof-muhit omillari muhim ahamiyat kasb etayotgan sharoitda (Liu et al., 2021).

Mazkur tadqiqotda mamlakatning turizm raqobatbardoshligini baholash uchun turli statistik usullarga asoslangan yangi modelni taklif etish ko'zda tutilgan. Ushbu yondashuv turizm siyosatini shakllantirishda ilmiy asoslangan qarorlar qabul qilish zaruratini asoslaydi (Liu et al., 2021). Taklif etilayotgan model turizm sohasida raqobatbardoshlikni shakllantirishda havo transporti infratuzilmasi, madaniy resurslar hamda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalariga (AKT) tayyorlik kabi omillarning hal qiluvchi rolini hisobga oladi (Fernández et al., 2019).

Ushbu model turizm rivojlanishi uchun muhim bo'lgan ko'rsatkichlarni aniqlash hamda ularning o'zaro bog'liqligini tahlil qilish orqali xalqaro va mahalliy turizm bozorlarida barqaror ustunlikka erishishga xizmat qiluvchi samarali strategiyalarni ishlab chiqish imkonini beradi (Fernández et al., 2019).

Tadqiqotchi N.J. Kang turizm raqobatbardoshligini o'rganishda dastlabki bosqich sifatida turistik yo'nalishlarning kuchli va zaif tomonlari, shuningdek, tashqi imkoniyatlari va tahdidlarini (SWOT tahlil) aniqlash zarurligini ta'kidlaydi (Gooroochurn & Sugiyarto, 2005).

Bundan tashqari, turistik destinatsiyalar raqobatbardoshligini o'rganishda Crouch va Ritchie modellariga asoslangan hamda 137 mamlakatni qamrab olgan Sayohat va turizm raqobatbardoshlik indeksi ma'lumotlaridan foydalanilgan tadqiqotlar ham mavjud. Ushbu tadqiqotlarda raqobatbardoshlik solishtirma ustunlik va raqobatbardosh ustunlik kabi ikki asosiy yo'nalish orqali tahlil qilingan (González-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

Mazkur yondashuvlar Crouch va Ritchie modelida ko'rsatilgan qo'llab-quvvatlovchi omillar va resurslar hamda Jahon Iqtisodiy Forumining infratuzilma bo'yicha baholashlari bilan uyg'unlashadi. Bu esa destinatsiyaning raqobatbardoshligini aniqlashda infratuzilma va boshqaruv imkoniyatlarining muhimligini yana bir bor tasdiqlaydi (Uyar et al., 2022).

Shunday qilib, turizm raqobatbardoshligini kompleks baholash nafaqat mavjud modellarni tanqidiy qayta ko'rib chiqishni, balki yangi, ko'p qirrali yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqishni ham talab etadi (Liu et al., 2021). Bunday yondashuvlar sayyohlik yo'nalishlarining raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlash jarayonida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan muammolarni chuqur tahlil qilish imkonini beradi hamda solishtirma va raqobatbardosh ustunlik kabi asosiy mezonlar asosida baholashni ta'minlaydi (González-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, turizm raqobatbardoshligini belgilovchi asosiy omillar qatoriga tabiiy resurslar, strategik joylashuv, xavfsizlik, joylashtirish infratuzilmasi, madaniy-tarixiy boyliklar hamda transport imkoniyatlari kiradi (Rheeders, 2022). Mazkur omillar, ayniqsa, turizm yo'nalishlarini rivojlantirish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi va ularning sifati hamda jozibadorligi raqobatbardosh ustunlikning asosiy manbai hisoblanadi (Luštický, 2019; Rheeders, 2022).

Turizm yo'nalishlarining raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashda nafaqat iqtisodiy, balki ekologik, ijtimoiy, madaniy va siyosiy barqarorlik ham muhim rol o'ynaydi (Sobirov et al., 2023; Uca & Yüncü, 2020). Shu bilan birga, ushbu omillarni kompleks baholash orqali destinatsiyaning kuchli va zaif tomonlarini aniqlash hamda uning rivojlanishi uchun zarur bo'lgan strategik ustunliklarni shakllantirish mumkin (Kovačević et al., 2017; Rheeders, 2022).

Bundan tashqari, ayrim tadqiqotchilar raqobatbardoshlikni raqiblariga nisbatan yuqori sifatli mahsulot va xizmatlar taklif etish qobiliyati sifatida talqin qiladilar. Bunda sayohat tajribasi sayyohlar uchun eng muhim omillardan biri hisoblanadi (Lesmana et al., 2022). Shu nuqtai nazardan, turizm infratuzilmasining, xususan, transport, joylashtirish vositalari, diqqatga sazovor obyektlar, xizmatlar va qulayliklarning rivojlanish darajasini oshirish turizm sifat ko'rsatkichlarini yaxshilash hamda raqobatbardoshlikni kuchaytirishda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi (Arabov et al., 2024).

Mazkur jarayon, o'z navbatida, mamlakatning umumiy turizm salohiyatini oshirishga va uning xalqaro miqyosdagi raqobatbardoshligini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi (Sobirov et al., 2023). Shu jihatdan, Lopez va boshqalar tomonidan PROMETHEE usuli asosida olib borilgan tadqiqotlar mintaqaviy turizm raqobatbardoshligini tahlil qilish hamda turistik yo'nalishlarning kuchli va zaif tomonlarini aniqlash imkonini bergan ("Spatial Classification of Tourism Routes in Isfahan Province, Iran," 2023).

Ushbu yondashuv turizm sohasida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish uchun maqsadli strategiyalarni ishlab chiqishga zamin yaratadi. Chunki bu sohadagi muvaffaqiyat nafaqat taklif etilayotgan mahsulot va xizmatlar sifatiga, balki bozor dinamikasiga moslashish qobiliyatiga ham bog'liq (Hoon-Ku et al., 2020).

Bundan tashqari, turizm raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashda marketing, ilmiy tadqiqotlar, siyosat, strategiya va barqarorlik kabi omillar muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi (Okroshidze et al., 2024). Crouch va Ritchie ta'kidlaganidek, turistik destinatsiyaning uzoq muddatli raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlash uchun qiyosiy va raqobatbardosh ustunliklarga ega bo'lish zarur (Chernega, 2021). Ushbu ustunliklar turistik mahsulotning yuqori sifati, narxlarning raqobatbardoshligi hamda innovatsion xizmatlar orqali shakllanadi (Savitska et al., 2015).

Shuningdek, Bordas raqobatbardoshlikni mamlakatlar kesimida emas, balki turistik klasterlar va turizm industriyalari darajasida mavjud deb hisoblaydi (Sobirov et al., 2023). Mazkur klasterlar, ayniqsa, mehmonxona xizmatlari, axborot portallari va boshqa infratuzilmalarni rivojlantirish orqali o'z raqobatbardoshligini oshirish imkoniyatiga ega (Миронов, 2023).

Demak, turizm raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashda nafaqat destinatsiyaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, balki turistik xizmatlarni taqdim etuvchi korxonalar hamda boshqa tashkilotlarning samaradorligi ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi (Enright & Newton, 2004). Bunda sayyohlik yo'nalishlarida faoliyat yuritayotgan subyektlarning samaradorligi, xizmatlarning optimal narx-sifat nisbati hamda iste'molchilar talabiga moslashuvchanligi muhim omillar sifatida namoyon bo'ladi (Hamidov et al., 2024).

Turistik destinatsiyalarning raqobatbardoshligini belgilovchi omillar majmuasi global va mahalliy turizm bozorlarida barqaror ustunlikka erishishda strategik ahamiyat kasb etadi hamda ularni doimiy monitoring qilish va takomillashtirishni talab etadi (Córdova-Buiza & Serruto-Perea, 2024; González-Rodríguez et al., 2023). Ushbu jarayon, ayniqsa, turizm sohasida tez o'zgaruvchan global muhit va kuchayib borayotgan raqobat bosimi sharoitida yanada dolzarb ahamiyatga ega (Luštický & Štumpf, 2021).

Turistik destinatsiyalar ichki va tashqi bozorlarda raqobatbardoshligini oshirish maqsadida o'ziga xos mavqe, identitet va individuallikni shakllantirish uchun brending usullaridan tobora keng foydalanmoqda (Kozak & Baloğlu, 2010). Bunday sharoitda marketing vositalarining destinatsiya marketingi va targ'ibotiga qo'shgan hissi, innovatsion yondashuvlar va xizmatlar sifati hamda destinatsiyaning o'ziga xosligini aks ettirish qobiliyati raqobatbardoshlikni sezilarli darajada oshiradi (Bajrami et al., 2017; Шпак et al., 2022).

Bundan tashqari, turizm destinatsiyalarida mahalliy aholining turmush sifatini yaxshilashga xizmat qiluvchi resurslar ham muhim omil hisoblanadi (CEVAHİR & Temeloğlu, 2022). Shu bilan birga, faol mehmonxona xo'jaliklarining mavjudligi va ularning xizmat ko'rsatish darajasi butun destinatsiya raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi (Tuna et al., 2019). Chunki turizm bozorining kengayib borishi natijasida har bir yo'nalish o'z ulushini oshirishga intiladi va bu holat makro hamda mikro darajadagi raqobatning kuchayishiga olib keladi (Uca & Yüncü, 2020).

Raqobat ustunligiga erishish uchun destinatsiyaning jozibadorligi va tashrif buyuruvchilarning tajribasi muqobil yo'nalishlarga nisbatan ustun bo'lishi zarur. Natijada, destinatsiyaning muvaffaqiyati nafaqat mavjud resurslarga, balki ularni samarali boshqarish hamda bozor talablariga mos ravishda rivojlantirish qobiliyatiga ham bog'liq (Uca & Yüncü, 2020).

Shu bois turistik destinatsiyalar uchun raqobatbardoshlikni ta'minlashda uzoq muddatli strategiyalarni qo'llash, mavjud imkoniyatlar, xarajatlar va kutilayotgan foydalarni kompleks ravishda hisobga olish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi (Çalışkan, 2019).

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Xulosa qilib aytganda, turistik destinatsiyalarning barqaror raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlash marketing strategiyalari, innovatsiyalar, barqarorlik amaliyotlari hamda iste'molchilarning o'zgaruvchan talablariga moslashish qobiliyatini o'z ichiga olgan kompleks yondashuvni talab etadi (Belarmino & Janaban, 2023; Pereira et al., 2025). Bu esa global turizm bozorida muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun doimiy moslashuvchanlik, innovatsiyalarni joriy etish va yuqori sifatli xizmatlar ko'rsatish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi (Buhalis, 2000).

Bundan tashqari, innovatsion brendlash strategiyalarini joriy etish orqali destinatsiyalar nafaqat o'ziga xos imijni shakllantiradi, balki sayyohlarning o'zgaruvchan talablariga mos keluvchi noyob tajribalarni ham taklif etadi (Aman et al., 2024; Ličanin, 2024). Bunday yondashuv destinatsiyaning bozor qiymatini oshirish bilan birga uning uzoq muddatli barqarorligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi (Baraniuk, 2021; UNUR & Cetin, 2017).

Mazkur jarayon strategik qarorlar qabul qilishni qo'llab-quvvatlab, turizm korxonalariga dinamik bozor muhitida yuzaga kelayotgan imkoniyatlardan samarali foydalanish imkonini beradi (Jansom & Yang, 2025). Barqaror rivojlanish va raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish uchun mahalliy hamjamiyatlar, turizm tashkilotlari, xususiy sektor hamda davlat institutlarini o'z ichiga olgan barcha manfaatdor tomonlarning integratsiyasi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi (Ličanin, 2024; Rashid, 2024).

Bunday hamkorlik turizm mahsulotining yaxlitligini ta'minlash va sayyohlar talabiga mos keluvchi turistik yo'nalishlarni rivojlantirishda turli subyektlar manfaatlarini muvozanatlashtirishni talab etadi (Baraniuk, 2021). Bu esa turizmning iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va ekologik jihatdan barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashga qaratilgan kompleks strategiyalarni ishlab chiqishni taqozo etadi (Belozerova et al., 2021).

Shu nuqtai nazardan, destinatsiyaning barqaror va innovatsion brendini shakllantirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Chunki bu sayyohlarning o'zgaruvchan afzalliklariga moslashish va raqobatbardosh bozorda ajralib turish imkonini beradi (Aman et al., 2024). Raqobatbardoshlikni ta'minlashda destinatsiya brendingining o'rni global turizm landshaftida tobora kengayib borayotgan ilmiy tadqiqot yo'nalishi sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda (Abashidze, 2024).

Shu sababli, destinatsiyalar o'zlarini raqobatchilardan farqlash hamda tashrif buyuruvchilarni, rezidentlarni va investorlarni jalb qilish maqsadida joy brendingi strategiyalaridan samarali foydalanishlari zarur (Escobar-Farfán et al., 2024).

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI

1. Abashidze, I. (2024). Destination branding for gaining a competitive edge in the global tourism landscape: Insights and prospects of the Georgian case. *Innovative Economics and Management*, 11(3), 47–58. <https://doi.org/10.46361/2449-2604.11.3.2024.47-58>
2. Aman, E. E., Papp-Váry, Á., Kangai, D., & Odunga, S. O. (2024). Building a sustainable future: Challenges, opportunities, and innovative strategies for destination branding in tourism. *Administrative Sciences*, 14(12), 312. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci14120312>
3. Arabov, N., Nasimov, D., Janzakov, B., Khomitov, K., Utemuratova, G., Abduraimov, D., & Ismailov, B. (2024). Shaping the future of Uzbekistan's tourism: An in-depth analysis of infrastructure influence and strategic planning. *Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research (JEECAR)*, 11(1), 53. <https://doi.org/10.15549/jeecar.v11i1.1478>
4. Ataberk, E. (2022). Foça ve Dikili'de turizmin coğrafi mekân üzerindeki etkileri: Süreç, dinamikler ve değişimlerin karşılaştırılması. *Tourism Academy Journal*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/touraj/issue/70329/980234>
5. Bajrami, D. D., Petrovic, M., & Radosavac, A. (2017). Competitiveness of rural tourism sector in Vojvodina: The analysis of key stakeholders' attitudes. *Megatrend Revija*, 14(2), 91–110. <https://doi.org/10.5937/megrev1702091d>
6. Baraniuk, D. (2021). Marketing approach to understanding, forming and developing tourist destinations. *Proceedings of Scientific Works of Cherkasy State Technological University. Series: Economic Sciences*, 63, 136–142. <https://doi.org/10.24025/2306-4420.63.2021.249631>
7. Belarmino, M. D., & Janaban, D. A. A. (2023). Marketing strategies, competitiveness and sustainability practices of tourist destinations. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies (IJSMS)*, 6(6), 111–126. <https://doi.org/10.51386/25815946/ijsms-v6i6p111>
8. Belozerova, O., Mirzoian, S., & Wagenseil, U. (2021). Optimizing the tourism destination potential with the integration of sustainability and innovation principles. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 295, 01055. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202129501055>
9. Buhalis, D. (2000). Marketing the competitive destination of the future. *Tourism Management*, 21(1), 97–116. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0261-5177\(99\)00095-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0261-5177(99)00095-3)
10. Çalışkan, U. (2019). How to develop tourism in the least developed regions? Notes from travel agencies. *Tourism Academy Journal*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/touraj/issue/46702/455327>
11. CEVAHİR, S., & Temeloğlu, E. (2022). Algılanan destinasyon rekabetçiliğinin değerlendirilmesine yönelik bir araştırma: Çanakkale örneği. *Gastronomy Studies Journal*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/gastoria/issue/73234/1091134>
12. Chernega, O. (2021). Assessment of the competitiveness of the tourist destination. *Economics, Entrepreneurship, Management*, 8(2), 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.23939/eem2021.02.008>
13. Córdova-Buiza, F., & Serruto-Perea, Y. A. (2024). The competitiveness of tourist destinations: A review of the scientific literature. *International Conference on Tourism Research*, 7(1), 47–58. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ictr.7.1.2146>

14. Díaz-Padilla, V. T., Travar, I., Acosta, Z., & Parra-López, E. (2023). Tourism competitiveness versus sustainability: Impact on the World Economic Forum model using the Rasch methodology. *Sustainability*, 15(18), 13700. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151813700>
15. Enright, M. J., & Newton, J. D. (2004). Tourism destination competitiveness: A quantitative approach. *Tourism Management*, 25(6), 777–788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2004.06.008>
16. Escobar-Farfán, M., Cervera, A., & Schlesinger, M. (2024). Destination brand identity: Challenges, opportunities, and future research agenda. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2024.2302803>
17. Fernández, J. A. S., Azevedo, P. S., Martín, J. M. M., & Martín, J. A. R. (2019). Determinants of tourism destination competitiveness in the countries most visited by international tourists: Proposal of a synthetic index. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 33, 100582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2019.100582>
18. González-Rodríguez, M. R., Fernández, M. del C. D., & Pulido-Pavón, N. (2023). Tourist destination competitiveness: An international approach through the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 47, 101127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2023.101127>
19. Gooroochurn, N., & Sugiyarto, G. (2005). Competitiveness indicators in the travel and tourism industry. *Tourism Economics*, 11(1), 25–43. <https://doi.org/10.5367/0000000053297130>
20. Göral, R., & Tengilimoğlu, E. (2018). Comparison of the Turkic world destinations tourism sector effectiveness. *Turkish World Studies Journal*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/tdtdad/issue/41442/455826>
21. Hamidov, S., Tokhirov, J., & Adizov, B. (2024). Processes of management of competitiveness of ecotourism destinations and methodology of its assessment. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 587, 05021. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202458705021>
22. Hefny, L. (2023). An overview of literature on destination competitiveness: A theoretical analysis of the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index. *PIJTH*, 2(2), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.21608/pijth.2023.253372.1006>
23. Hong, W. (2009). Global competitiveness measurement for the tourism sector. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 12(2), 105–132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500802596359>
24. Hoon-Ku, S., Chi, X., & Han, H. (2020). Measurement development for tourism destination business environment and competitive advantages. *Sustainability*, 12(20), 8587. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208587>
25. Jansom, A., & Yang, C.-H. (2025). The evolution of innovative marketing and branding in tourism: A systematic review of entrepreneurial challenges and strategic trends. *TEM Journal*, 14(3), 2769–2780. <https://doi.org/10.18421/tem143-77>
26. Khelashvili, I., & Okroshidze, L. (2025). Exploring the tourism competitiveness of a destination: A case study of Georgia. *Sustainability*, 17(8), 3342. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17083342>
27. Kim, Y. R., Liu, A., & Williams, A. M. (2021). Competitiveness in the visitor economy: A systematic literature review. *Tourism Economics*, 28(3), 817–835. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13548166211034437>
28. Kovačević, N. D., Kovačević, L., Stankov, U., Dragičević, V., & Miletić, A. (2017). Applying destination competitiveness model to strategic tourism development of small destinations: The case of South Banat district. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 8, 114–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2017.01.002>
29. Kozak, M., & Baloğlu, Ş. (2010). Managing and marketing tourist destinations: Strategies to gain a competitive edge. *Japan Society of Medical Entomology and Zoology*. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BB04109239>
30. Lesmana, H., Sugiyarto, S., Yosevina, C., & Widjojo, H. (2022). A competitive advantage model for Indonesia's sustainable tourism destinations from supply and demand side perspectives. *Sustainability*, 14(24), 16398. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416398>
31. Ličanin, B. (2024). Brendiranje turističke destinacije. *Media Culture and Public Relations*, 15(2), 145–154. <https://doi.org/10.63191/mcpr.15.2.6>
32. Liu, Y.-L., Ko, P.-F., & Chiang, J.-T. (2021). Developing an evaluation model for monitoring country-based tourism competitiveness. *SAGE Open*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211047559>
33. Luštický, M. (2019). Stakeholders' role in a model of tourism destination competitiveness. *Auspicia*, 16(1), 18–30. https://doi.org/10.36682/a_2019_1_2
34. Luštický, M., & Štumpf, P. (2021). Leverage points of tourism destination competitiveness dynamics. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 38, 100792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2021.100792>
35. Marynyak, Y., & Stetsko, N. (2021). Perspectives of digital transformation of the tourist sector of the economy of Ukraine. *Scientific Issues of Ternopil Volodymyr Hnatiuk National Pedagogical University. Series: Geography*, 50(1), 102–110. <https://doi.org/10.25128/2519-4577.21.1.12>
36. Novais, M. A., Ruhanen, L., & Arcodia, C. (2015). Destination competitiveness: What we know, what we know but shouldn't and what we don't know but should. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 19(6), 492–512. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2015.1091443>
37. Okroshidze, L., Meyer, D., & Khelashvili, I. (2024). An assessment of tourism competitiveness: A comparative analysis of Georgia and neighboring countries. *Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research (JEECAR)*, 11(2), 377–390. <https://doi.org/10.15549/jeecar.v11i2.1536>
38. Pereira, J. M., Almeida, P., & Almeida, G. G. F. (2025). Bibliometric analysis of key variables in tourism: Destination, competitiveness, image, quality, and tourist satisfaction (2000–2023). *Administrative Sciences*, 15(2), 69. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci15020069>
39. Rashid, A. (2024). Research on tourism competitiveness. *ResearchHub*. <https://doi.org/10.55277/researchhub.vq5dnd6h>
40. Rheeders, T. (2022). A review of the determinants of tourism destination competitiveness. *Journal of Contemporary Management*, 19(2), 238–255. <https://doi.org/10.35683/jcman1008.166>

41. Safarov, B., & Janzakov, B. (2021). Measuring competitiveness in tourism enterprises using an integral index. *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 37(3), 768–775. <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.37305-707>
42. Savitska, O. P., Novostavskaya, O. I., & Savitska, N. V. (2015). Formation of competitive potential of tourism enterprises under sustainable development conditions. *Scientific Bulletin of UNFU*, 25(9), 166–172. <https://doi.org/10.15421/40250925>
43. Shabanova, L. B., Yusupova, G., & Kabirov, I. R. (2022). Transformation of the tourism industry after COVID-19 pandemic and sanctions. *Bulletin of Kemerovo State University. Series: Political, Sociological and Economic Sciences*, 7(4), 511–520. <https://doi.org/10.21603/2500-3372-2022-7-4-511-520>
44. Sobirov, B., Poltorak, A. S., Alimova, M., Matkarimov, K., & Shadiyeva, D. (2023). Factors of competitiveness of the tourism sector. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 452, 07013. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202345207013>
45. Spatial classification of tourism routes in Isfahan Province, Iran. (2023). *Human Geographies – Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography*, 17(2). <https://doi.org/10.5719/hgeo.2023.172.3>
46. Tuna, M., Türkmenbaş, Z., & Keleş, A. (2019). Determinants of pricing in coastal hotels: A stakeholder perspective. *Tourism Academy Journal*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/touraj/issue/50389/554607>
47. Ubavic, P. (2016). Positioning of Serbia as a tourism destination on the international tourist market. *Megatrend Revija*, 13(2), 97–110. <https://doi.org/10.5937/megrev1602097u>
48. Uca, S., & Yüncü, H. R. (2020). Ecological performance of Mediterranean tourism destinations according to the Environmental Performance Index (2020): A multidimensional scaling analysis. *Journal of Gastronomy, Hospitality and Tourism*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/joghat/issue/59161/850884>
49. UNUR, K., & Cetin, N. (2017). Local tourists' brand perceptions of Kizkalesi as a tourism destination. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary and Intercultural Research*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/iicder/issue/31656/347077>
50. Uyar, A., Kuzey, C., Köseoğlu, M. A., & Karaman, A. S. (2022). Travel and tourism competitiveness index and tourism sector development. *Tourism Economics*, 29(4), 1005–1023. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13548166221080357>
51. Vošta, M., & Abrahám, J. (2015). Global tourism and implications for the Czech Republic. *Acta Oeconomica Pragensia*, 23(4), 63–73. <https://doi.org/10.18267/j.aop.481>
52. Deiak, B. S., & Kushnir, N. (2022). Svitova hotelno-restoranna industriia v umovakh mizhnarodnoi konkurentsii [Global hotel and restaurant industry in conditions of international competition]. *Efektivna Ekonomika*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.32702/2307-2105.2022.12.54>
53. Myronov, Yu. B. (2023). Klasterna model rozvytku turystychnoi destynatsii [Cluster model of tourism destination development]. *Industriia Turyzmu i Hostynnosti v Tsentralnii ta Skhidnii Yevropi*, 8, 20–27. <https://doi.org/10.32782/tourismhospcee-8-3>
54. Shpak, N., Muzychenko-Kozlovska, O., Gvozd, M., Sroka, W., & Havryliuk, M. (2022). Comprehensive assessment of the influence of factors on the attractiveness of a country's tourism brand: A model approach. *Journal of Tourism and Services*, 13(24), 209–223. <https://doi.org/10.29036/jots.v13i24.354>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
